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Impact of Prolate Ablations Optical Zone Width on Refractive Stability in Hyperopic Presbyopic Patients: A Retrospective Analysis

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Abstract:	<p>Purpose: To examine how aspheric (prolate) ablation geometry—in particular the optical-zone (OZ) diameter of the prolate component—relates to the early refractive effect and 12–24-month hyperopic regression after hyperopic LASIK in presbyopic eyes.</p> <p>Methods: Single-centre retrospective series. Treatments used customized prolate ablations (pure prolate or hyperopic-biased prolate) planned on a prolate OZ (QOZ) distinct from the spherical-correction OZ. Primary outcome: hyperopic regression; secondary: spherical effect. Exposures: OZ width, prolatization magnitude (Q-factor), and intended spherical component. Continuous associations were estimated by linear regression; contrast of extremes quartiles (Q4 vs Q1) by ordinary least squares with heteroskedasticity-consistent (HC2) standard errors. Benjamini–Hochberg FDR ($q=0.05$) controlled multiplicity. A pure-prolate subgroup was analyzed at 1 month.</p> <p>Results: Pure prolate ($n=51$): Q-factor showed a weak association with spherical effect ($R^2=0.07$); Q4 vs Q1 not significant ($\Delta=-0.479$ D; $p = 0.045$; $q = 0.056$). In contrast, larger prolate OZ was linked to a more myopic early effect ($R^2=0.16$; $\Delta=-0.562$ D; $p=0.0126$; $q=0.022$). Whole cohort: Prolatization magnitude was associated with greater hyperopic regression ($\Delta=+0.388$ D; $p<0.0001$; $q<0.0005$). Larger OZ also showed greater regression ($\Delta=+0.270$ D; $p=0.013$; $q=0.022$). In this cohort, the intended spherical component showed no material association with regression ($\Delta=+0.065$ D; $p\approx 0.55$; $q\approx 0.66$).</p> <p>Conclusions: In presbyopic hyperopic LASIK, a wider prolate optical zone yields a more myopic early effect but is associated with greater hyperopic regression over 12–24 months; greater prolatization likewise predicts more regression. These exploratory findings support Dual-Zone (Non-Coextensive) Planning (DZP)—separating the spherical/myopic and prolate components—to improve spherical-equivalent (SEQ) stability.</p>
Author Comments:	

1 Introduction

2

3 Presbyopia is essentially universal beyond the fifth decade and hyperopia is common in adults, both bur-
4 dens increasing with age.¹ Despite this need, corneal refractive surgery has been dominated by myopic
5 corrections²; procedures for hyperopic candidates have seen more limited adoption owing to concerns
6 about the size of the functional optical zone, induction of higher-order aberrations, centration sensitivity,
7 and long-term stability in hyperopic LASIK—factors determined by the width of the treated optical zone.

8

9 Hyperopic LASIK remains constrained by postoperative hyperopic regression. Enlarging the opti-
10 cal/transition zones is the conventional strategy to mitigate drift, and larger zones have been associated
11 with improved predictability in hyperopic ablations.³⁻⁷ In presbyopic hyperopes, surgeons may incorporate
12 prolate (asphericity-enhancing) ablations—parameterized by the corneal Q-factor (shape metric) or by
13 primary spherical aberration (Z_4^0 , C12)—with or without a mild myopic bias.⁸⁻¹²

14

15 How the planned optical-zone (OZ) diameter of the aspheric component—potentially distinct from the
16 spherical-correction OZ—interacts with prolate profiles to influence the early refractive effect and long-
17 term stability is insufficiently defined.

18 We address this gap by retrospectively analyzing presbyopic hyperopic eyes treated with customized pro-
19 late ablations (pure prolate and myopic-biased prolate) delivered over varying OZ diameters. We prespec-
20 ified two objectives: (i) quantify the early spherical effect (baseline→1 month) and (ii) quantify hyperopic
21 regression thereafter (≥ 12 months), as functions of OZ width and prolatization magnitude; the intended
22 spherical component was evaluated as a negative control exposure.

23

24 Mechanistic premise. We hypothesize that long-term stability is governed less by local slope (gradient)
25 than by the radius at which the ablation reaches its maximum, with particular concern when the ablation

26 peak lies in the ~3-mm paracentral annulus. This retrospective analysis probes that premise; results are
27 hypothesis-generating.

28 Methods

29

30 Design and participants. Single-centre retrospective series of presbyopic hyperopic LASIK cases planned
31 with prolatizing aspheric modulation. Inclusion required: age 50–59 years, stable refraction (≤ 0.50 D
32 change over ≥ 12 months), clear lens (no visually significant cataract), normal corneal topogra-
33 phy/tomography, central corneal thickness and residual stromal bed within manufacturer safety limits, and
34 absence of ocular surface disease impacting measurements. Eligible eyes had a documented preoperative
35 manifest refraction and uneventful surgery, preoperative manifest spherical equivalent between $+0.00$ and
36 $+4.00$ D (positive = hyperopic) and refractive cylinder up to 1.00 D (absolute value). When both eyes
37 were eligible, one eye per patient was selected at baseline using a deterministic coin-flip based on de-
38 vice's patient ID number (even parity = right eye [OD]; odd parity = left eye [OS]): selection did not de-
39 pend on dominance, exposures, outcomes, or follow-up completeness.

40

41 Exclusion criteria. Eyes were excluded if they had postoperative complications liable to compromise reli-
42 able refraction (e.g., flap/interface complications, epithelial ingrowth, clinically significant surface irregu-
43 larity), if they underwent any enhancement or re-treatment during follow-up, or if there was a history of
44 prior ocular surgery or ocular disease (see ocular surface status below) likely to affect refraction or corneal
45 optics.

46

47 Ocular surface status. Clinically significant dry eye disease (DED) at screening was an exclusion criteri-
48 on; such eyes were not operated and are not represented in this cohort. During follow-up, refraction and
49 acuity were obtained only under a clinically stable tear film. Incident DED was defined pragmatically as
50 symptomatic ocular surface disease requiring therapeutic escalation (e.g., prescription anti-inflammatory
51 drops, punctal plugs) or clinical signs judged to compromise reliable measurements (e.g., diffuse corneal
52 staining, markedly unstable tear film).

53

54 Surgical plans and ablation profiles. Cases comprised pure prolate (asphericity-enhancing) treatments
55 with or without an additional spherical component when a near-vision boost was required. The pro-
56 late/aspheric modulation was delivered on an optical zone (QOZ) distinct from the optical zone (OZ) used
57 for the spherical correction. LASIK treatments performed by a single surgeon (the author) between July
58 2020 and September 2023 at Laser Vision Bour-
59 gogne (Chalon-sur-Saône, France) using an excimer laser (TENE0 317, Model 1, Technolas Perfect Vi-
60 sion GmbH [Bausch + Lomb], Munich, Germany). Flaps were created with a femtosec-
61 ond laser (FEMTO LDV Z2, Ziemer Ophthalmic Systems AG, Port, Switzerland), intended thickness 110
62 μm , diameter 9.50 mm, hinge superior. Ablations were centered on the pupil center under photopic condi-
63 tions. The spherical-correction transition zone was 1.07 mm; the prolate/aspheric transition zone was 0.70
64 mm. Planned Q-factor modulation (more positive Q denoting greater prolatization) was recorded from the
65 laser planning logs. When near support was desired, a minimal myopic target of $[-0.50 \text{ to } -0.75]$ D was
66 used (monocular or micro-monovision per surgeon judgment). Prolate/aspheric modulation was titrated
67 by ocular dominance: minimal (or no) prolatization was planned for the dominant eye, and mild prolatiza-
68 tion for the non-dominant eye. To deliver the aspheric (prolate) component, the laser console requires a
69 minimal myopic offset ($\approx -0.30 \text{ to } -0.13$ D), which cannot be set to plano; this offset was accounted for.
70 Postoperative regimen: topical azithromycin + ofloxacin for 3 days and a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory
71 (flurbiprofen) for 3 days; lubricants as needed.

72

73 Preoperative imaging and metrics. Preoperative anterior corneal Q and mean keratometry (Km) were ac-
74 quired with a slit-scan elevation topographer (ORBSCAN 3, Technolas Perfect Vision GmbH [Bausch +
75 Lomb], Munich, Germany). Primary spherical aberration (6mm Z_4^0 , C12) under cycloplegia (1% tropi-
76 camide) was obtained on a Shack–Hartmann wavefront-sensor aberrometer (ZYWAVE 3, Technolas Per-
77 fect Vision GmbH [Bausch + Lomb], Munich, Germany).

78

79 Ethics and data protection. This retrospective, non-interventional study complied with the Declaration of
80 Helsinki and the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR/MR-004). All patients provided written
81 informed consent permitting the research use of their clinical data; all data were de-identified prior to
82 analysis, the study was recorded with the institution's Data Protection Officer. All procedures were per-
83 formed as part of routine clinical care at the treating surgeon's discretion using commercially available la-
84 ser platforms; treatment parameters (e.g., Q-factor modulation, prolate/aspheric profiles, and optical-zone
85 diameters) reflected individualized planning and were not assigned for research purposes. No additional
86 procedures, examinations, or data collection were performed solely for research. Under local regulations,
87 retrospective, non-interventional analysis of routine-care data did not require CPP/IRB approval.

88

89 Assessments and follow-up. Monocular uncorrected distance visual acuity (UDVA) was measured at a 6-
90 m equivalent optical path using a front-surface mirror and a logMAR-compliant distance chart (Sloan
91 optotypes; five letters per line; 0.10-logMAR increments), calibrated so that the 0.00-logMAR line sub-
92 tended 5 arcmin at 6 m. Room luminance was maintained at photopic level, high-contrast optotypes. Acu-
93 ities were line-scored and reported in logMAR. Manifest refraction (sphere (Sph), cylinder (Cyl); spheri-
94 cal equivalent: $SEQ = Sph + Cyl/2$) was obtained at 1 month, 3–6 months, and 12–24 months postopera-
95 tively. When multiple visits occurred within a window, the last measurement within that window was re-
96 tained. Uncorrected and corrected distance visual acuities were recorded. Near visual acuity (UNVA),
97 measured monocularly and binocularly, was systematically collected but is not analyzed in this report.

98

99 Distance performance and safety metrics. At 12–24 months, we summarized distance performance using
100 the cumulative distribution of monocular UDVA at standard Snellen-equivalent thresholds, displayed
101 alongside preoperative monocular CDVA as a contextual benchmark. Safety was assessed as change in
102 monocular CDVA from baseline expressed in ETDRS lines (1 line = 0.10 logMAR). All acuities were
103 measured in logMAR and converted to Snellen for display only. Because several profiles intentionally

104 imparted a mild myopic bias to support near vision, UDVA was interpreted as a distance-acuity trade-off
105 rather than a safety endpoint; safety was defined strictly by CDVA change.

106

107 Outcomes and statistical analysis. The primary outcome was hyperopic regression in manifest spherical
108 equivalent refraction stability (SEQRS), defined as $SEQRS = SEQ_{12-24mo} - SEQ_{1mo}$

109 with positive values denoting hyperopic drift. The secondary outcome was the achieved SEQ $ASEQ =$

110 $SEQ_{1mo} - SEQ_{preop}$.

111

112 Exposures. (i) Optical-zone width (mm) for the relevant ablation, (ii) magnitude of prolatization (Q-factor
113 / planned aspheric modulation), and (iii) intended spherical component (D). Subgroup analyses isolated
114 the pure prolate cohort; whole-cohort analyses included all eyes.

115

116 Modeling strategy. Exposures were first analyzed continuously using linear regression, reporting the slope
117 β (effect per unit exposure), 95% CI, two-sided p-value, and R^2 . Because linearity was not assumed a pri-
118 ori, we prespecified a complementary contrast of extremes (Q4 vs Q1) estimated by ordinary least squares
119 with heteroskedasticity-consistent (Huber–White, HC2) standard errors; results are reported as Δ_{Q4-Q1} with
120 95% CI. For inferential reporting, the Q4–Q1 contrast was tested with Welch’s t(df) two-sample t-test
121 (unequal variances) using Satterthwaite degrees of freedom. Analyses were complete-case; no imputation
122 was performed.

123

124 Multiplicity. Five prespecified primary comparisons (extreme quartiles; two-sided) were tested:

125 (1) 1-month achieved SEQ in the pure-prolate subgroup by prolatization magnitude (Q-factor);

126 (2) 1-month achieved SEQ in the pure-prolate subgroup by optical-zone width (ZOQ);

127 (3) 12–24-month hyperopic regression in the whole cohort by intended spherical component;

128 (4) 12–24-month hyperopic regression in the whole cohort by prolatization magnitude (Q-factor);

129 (5) 12–24-month hyperopic regression in the whole cohort by optical-zone width.

130 Across this single exploratory family, we controlled the false discovery rate (FDR) at 5% using the Ben-
131 jamini–Hochberg procedure (BH-FDR, $q = 0.05$). We report raw p-values and BH-adjusted q-values; dis-
132 coveries were declared at $q < 0.05$. All tests were two-sided.

133

134 Software. Analyses were performed in Python using pandas, NumPy, SciPy, and Matplotlib.

135 Data availability. De-identified participant data underlying the findings are available from the correspond-
136 ing author upon reasonable request.

137 Results

138

139 Cohort. Table 1 summarizes demographics for 221 eyes (107 right, 114 left) from 221 patients aged 50–
140 59 years with follow-up 370–715 days, and table 2 shows treatments parameters distributions. Follow-up
141 completeness: of 221 eyes, 221 (100%) had 1-month examination, 128 (58%) had 3–6-month data, and
142 221 (100%) had 12–24-mo data.

143

144 Distance performance and safety (12–24 months). The cumulative UDVA curve tracked the preoperative
145 CDVA benchmark across standard thresholds (Fig. 1A). Most eyes showed no change in CDVA (Fig.
146 1B). Figures 1C and 1D show SEQ and Cylinder accuracies. Figure 1E shows attempted VS achieved
147 SEQ and figure 1F shows the SEQ evolution.

148

149 Pure prolate cohort at 1 month (n = 51). Fig. 2A shows the net spherical-equivalent (SEQ) effect for pure
150 prolate treatments (no intentional myopic bias; the console enforces a default correction of -0.25 D): -0.25
151 ± 0.61 D (mean \pm SD). A continuous analysis indicated only a weak association between Q-factor modu-
152 lation and early SE ($R^2 = 0.07$; $\beta = +0.23$ D per 1.0 Q, i.e., $+0.023$ D per 0.1 Q). The contrast of extremes
153 (Q4 vs Q1) did not show a difference: $\Delta_{Q4-Q1} = -0.479$ D; 95% CI, -0.946 to -0.012; $df = 18$; $p = 0.045$; $q =$
154 0.056 ; Fig. 2B.

155 Optical-zone width (aspheric component) at 1 month (pure prolate, n = 51). Fig. 3A shows the continuous
156 association between optical-zone width for the prolate component and 1-month SE ($R^2 = 0.16$; $\beta = -0.39$
157 D per 1.0 mm, i.e., -0.039 D per 0.1 mm). The contrast of extremes (Q4 vs Q1) showed a more myopic
158 early effect in the widest-OZ quartile: $\Delta_{Q4-Q1} = -0.562$ D; 95% CI, -0.991 to -0.134; $df = 20.7$; $p = 0.0126$;
159 $q = 0.022$; Fig. 3B.

160

161 Whole cohort (n = 221). Intended spherical component (for near support). The intended spherical offset
162 averaged -1.132 ± 1.19 D. SEQ trajectories stratified by intended sphere showed no material separation

163 over time (Fig. 4A). The contrast of extremes (Q4 vs Q1) likewise showed no significant difference

164 ($\Delta_{Q4-Q1} = +0.065$ D; 95% CI, -0.151 to $+0.281$; $df = 107$; $p \approx 0.55$; $q \approx 0.55$; Fig. 4B).

165 Prolate (aspheric) magnitude. Figure 5A depicts SEQ trajectories stratified by Q-factor. The contrast of

166 extremes (Q4 vs Q1) showed greater hyperopic regression in the highest-prolatization quartile ($\Delta_{Q4-Q1} =$

167 $+0.388$ D; 95% CI, 0.206 to 0.570 ; $df \approx 101$; $p < 0.0001$; $q = 0.00025$; Fig. 5B).

168 Optical-zone width. Figure 6A depicts SEQ trajectories stratified by QOZ. The contrast of extremes (Q4

169 vs Q1) showed greater hyperopic regression in the widest-OZ quartile ($\Delta_{Q4-Q1} = +0.270$ D; 95% CI, 0.057

170 to 0.483 ; $df \approx 108$; $p = 0.013$; $q = 0.022$; Fig. 6B).

171

172 Summary. In pure prolate eyes, largest optical zones produced a more myopic early effect in this specific

173 cohort; in the full cohort, greater prolatization and wider optical zones were each associated with more

174 hyperopic regression over time.

175 Discussion

176

177 Limitations. This study is retrospective, single-center, with treatment choices (optical-zone width, magni-
178 tude of prolatization, intended spherical offset) determined clinically rather than assigned—raising the
179 possibility of confounding by indication and selection bias. The contrast-of-extremes analyses (especially
180 in the pure-prolate subgroup, $n \approx 51$; ≈ 13 eyes per quartile) suffer from limited power and information loss,
181 and may be vulnerable to winner's-curse inflation of effect sizes. Continuous models yielded low coeffi-
182 cients of determination ($R^2 \approx 0.07$ – 0.16), indicating substantial unexplained variance; linearity cannot be
183 assumed, and potential nonlinear relationships were not comprehensively modeled. We controlled multi-
184 plicity for the five prespecified comparisons using false discovery rate procedures (Benjamini–Hochberg,
185 $q < 0.05$); while appropriate for exploratory work, FDR does not control the family-wise error rate, and in-
186 ferences should be interpreted accordingly.

187 Measurement considerations may introduce additional noise. UDVA was obtained at a 6m equivalent dis-
188 tance using a front-surface mirror, which entails a nominal vergence of -0.17 D; manifest refraction
189 without systematic cycloplegia can leave residual accommodative noise (likely small in presbyopes but
190 nonzero). Follow-up used broad windows (1 month, 3–6 months, 12–24 months), and the last measure-
191 ment within each window was retained; this approach heterogenizes the time horizon (≈ 370 – 715 days),
192 may mix different regression kinetics, and is susceptible to attrition bias.

193 Potential unmeasured confounders include photopic/mesopic pupil size, ocular surface status, epithelial
194 remodeling, and postoperative higher-order aberrations—none of which were comprehensively quantified
195 here. We did not measure the functional optical zone (FOZ), modulation transfer function (MTF), or pa-
196 tient-reported outcomes (PROs); thus, the primary endpoint (Δ SEQ) reflects refractive stability rather
197 than optical/visual quality.

198 Generalizability is limited: findings depend on a specific device definition of the prolate optical-zone met-
199 ric (ZOQ). Overall, the associations reported should be viewed as hypothesis-generating and warrant pro-

200 spectively validation with Family-Wise Error Rate-controlled confirmatory testing, richer optical metrics,
201 and standardized planning parameters.

202

203 Findings. The data indicate that the achieved (1-month) refractive effect exhibits at most a weak linear
204 dependence on the degree of Q-factor (prolatization) modulation, rendering this association difficult to
205 identify with precision. Nevertheless, when pure aspheric (prolate) ablations are delivered over larger op-
206 tical zones, a small myopic early shift can be observed—an effect that may secondarily improve near vi-
207 sion—whereas smaller optical zones are classically associated with a hyperopic drift. Finally, the results
208 support the mechanistic hypothesis that prolatizing aspheric correction contributes to hyperopic regres-
209 sion, with the magnitude of prolatization and the optical-zone width acting as determinants. These infer-
210 ences are exploratory and should be confirmed in prospective clinical studies before informing definitive
211 practice.

212

213 Discussion—mechanistic synthesis. Prior work on corneal refractive surgery has consistently shown that
214 regression after hyperopic-oriented treatments depends on the optical-zone (OZ) diameter³⁻⁷: smaller OZs
215 are more prone to postoperative drift, whereas larger OZs tend to be more stable (at the cost of tissue). In
216 our series, the continuous dependence of the early (1-month) SEQ on the Q-factor modulation was at
217 most weak, but two findings are salient: (i) pure prolate ablations delivered over wide OZs can produce a
218 small myopic early shift—with potential near-vision benefit—whereas small OZs classically favor an ear-
219 ly hyperopic tendency; and (ii) long-term (12–24 months), greater prolatization and wider OZs are both
220 associated with more hyperopic regression. Collectively, the findings are insufficiently accounted for by a
221 gradient-driven regression mechanism¹³⁻¹⁴: a wide aspheric (prolate) optical zone does not inherently gen-
222 erate steep curvature gradients.

223 We propose a geometric, ring-based interpretation that better integrates our results with clinical experi-
224 ence. Specifically, regression risk appears heightened when the ablation peak lies within the paracentral
225 ring at ~3 mm from the corneal apex—regardless of whether the underlying profile is hyperopic or pure

226 prolate. This annular-risk region is shared by both profile families within common planning ranges: for
227 example, a hyperopic OZ ≈ 6 mm places the maximum ablation depth at $r \approx \text{OZ}/2 \approx 3$ mm, whereas a
228 wide-zone pure-prolate design (e.g., OZ ≈ 8.5 mm) places the maximum peak at $r \approx \text{OZ}/(2\sqrt{2}) \approx 3$ mm—
229 i.e., within the same inner paracentral annulus. On this view, the radial location of the ablation maxi-
230 mum—not merely the local gradient—could be a more proximate determinant of long-term hyperopic
231 drift.

232 This mechanistic synthesis aligns with the multifactorial nature of regression in hyperopic/presbyopic
233 profiles³: predominant epithelial remodeling (central thinning with paracentral thickening) tends to “fill
234 in” a paracentral ablation ring; flap–stromal biomechanics and stromal healing can add modest contractile
235 tendencies; and age-related lenticular changes in hyperopes (reduced accommodation, lens sclerosis) fur-
236 ther bias outcomes toward hyperopia over time. The annular-risk hypothesis provides a unifying pathway
237 through which these processes act preferentially when the maximum ablation depth is near ~ 3 mm radius.

238
239 Clinical implications. If confirmed prospectively, planning should decouple the two intents: use a large
240 OZ for any myopic bias aimed at near support, but keep prolate/aspheric modulation on a smaller, distinct
241 OZ that avoids placing the ablation peak in the ~ 3 mm ring. In practical terms, the goal is to minimize ab-
242 lation in that paracentral annulus—rather than “flattening gradients”—to reduce hyperopic regression.

243 Prospective studies with standardized OZ geometry, epithelial mapping, higher-order aberration profiling,
244 and functional optical zone quantification are warranted to validate and refine this principle.

245 Ethical considerations and planning implications. Given the observed association between wide-zone pure
246 aspheric (prolate) profiles and greater hyperopic regression in this series, it would be premature—and eth-
247 ically questionable—to promote large-zone, prolate-only ablations as stability-enhancing outside of pro-
248 spective, adequately monitored studies. The purpose of reporting these non-reassuring clinical observa-
249 tions is precisely to document the pitfall and avoid reproducing it.

250 As a pragmatic interim approach, we recommend Dual-Zone (Non-Coextensive) Planning (DZP): use a
251 larger optical zone for the spherical correction (when a near-vision bias is desired) and confine the pro-

252 late/aspheric modulation to a smaller, different zone. This separation is hypothesized to improve durabil-
253 ity by avoiding geometries that promote long-term drift. Until prospective confirmation is available,
254 wide-zone, prolate-only treatments should be undertaken with caution, with explicit informed consent re-
255 garding current evidence on regression risk.

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328 Captions

329

330

331 Table 1: Baseline demographics and preoperative characteristics (n = 221 eyes).

332 Note: Values are mean \pm SD. Abbreviations—UDVA: uncorrected distance visual acuity (logMAR);

333 SEQ: spherical equivalent (SEQ = Sphere + Cylinder/2); Km: mean anterior corneal keratometry (D); Q:

334 anterior corneal Q-factor; Z_s/C12: primary spherical aberration (μ m, 6-mm pupil).

335

336 Table 2: Treatment planning parameters.

337 Note: Values are mean \pm SD [min–max]. Units—SE in diopters (positive = hyperopic); Optical Zone

338 (OZ)/QOZ in mm; Q-factor dimensionless.

339

340 Figure 1. Distance performance and safety (12–24 months).

341 (A) Cumulative monocular UDVA with preoperative monocular CDVA as benchmark.

342 (B) Change in monocular CDVA from baseline (ETDRS lines).

343 (C) Postoperative SEQ Accuracy (12-24 mo)

344 (D) Postoperative Cylinder Accuracy (12-24 mo)

345 (E) Achieved SEQ vs Attempted SEQ (12-24 mo)

346 (F) SEQ hyperopic regression (12-24 months follow-up)

347 Abbreviations: UDVA, uncorrected distance visual acuity; CDVA, corrected distance visual acuity.

348

349 Figure 2. Pure prolate cohort: Q-factor and early refractive effect (1 month).

350 Achieved SEQ vs planned Q-factor (linear fit, R²)

351 Achieved SEQ vs planned Q-factor in quartiles

352 Note: Estimates by Ordinary Least Squares with HC2 Standard Errors.

353

354 Figure 3. Pure prolate cohort: Q-factor optical-zone width and achieved SEQ (1 month).

355 Achieved SEQ vs Q-factor Optical Zone width (linear fit, R²)

356 Achieved SEQ vs Q-factor Optical Zone width in quartiles

357

358 Figure 4. Whole cohort: intended spherical component and hyperopic regression (12–24 mo).

359 (A) SEQ hyperopic regression trajectories by intended Sphere Equivalent

360 (B) SEQ hyperopic regression at 12–24 months in quartiles

361

362 Figure 5. Whole cohort: prolatization magnitude and hyperopic regression (12–24 mo).

363 (A) SEQ hyperopic regression trajectories by planned Q-factor

364 (B) SEQ hyperopic regression at 12–24 months in quartiles

365

366 Figure 6. Whole cohort: optical-zone width and hyperopic regression (12–24 mo).

367 (A) SEQ hyperopic regression trajectories by Optical Zone width

368 SEQ hyperopic regression at 12–24 months in quartiles

Table 1

Characteristic (n=221)	Mean \pm SD (Min-Max)
Preop UDVA (logMAR)	0.28 \pm 0.18 (-0.8 to 0.00)
Preop Manifest Refraction SEQ (D)	1.26 \pm 1.05 (-0.12 to 4.00)
Preop corneal Km (D)	43.7 \pm 1.38 (40.20–46.90)
Preop corneal Q (dimensionless)	-0.17 \pm 0.12 (-0.50 to 0.17)
Preop Z40/C12 (μ m RMS)	0.23 \pm 0.12 (-0.05 to 0.65)

Table 2

Parameter (n=221)	Mean \pm SD (Min-Max)
Correction SEQ (D)	0.97 \pm 0.92 (-0.25 to 3.95)
Correction SEQ Optical Zone (mm)	7.42 \pm 0.45 (6.00–8.50)
Correction Q-factor (dimensionless)	1.17 \pm 0.59 (0.50–3.00)
Correction Q-factor Optical Zone (mm)	7.29 \pm 0.71 (6.00–8.50)

